

Understanding Directional Thermal Transport and Grain Boundary Thermal Resistance via Frequency Domain ThermoReflectance

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Abstract

Grain boundaries in crystalline materials significantly influence thermal transport, yet their directional and geometric effects remain challenging to characterize with conventional models. Traditional definitions of thermal boundary resistance (TBR) treat interfaces as infinitely thin discontinuities, neglecting the finite width and anisotropic nature of real grain boundaries. In this work, we introduce a rigorous extension of the Gibbs Excess methodology to quantify grain boundary thermal resistance in a geometry-preserving and directionally sensitive manner. We derive the Gibbs Excess formulation in both 1D and 3D, and demonstrate its applicability to Frequency Domain ThermoReflectance (FDTR) experiments through numerical simulations. To enhance directional sensitivity in FDTR, we implement a ring-shaped super-Gaussian pump profile and show improved in-plane and cross-plane resolution via sensitivity analysis and brute-force fitting. Numerical validation confirms that the Gibbs Excess framework recovers known limits in the 1D case and offers qualitative consistency with directional resistance trends in 3D, including variation with interface thickness and tilt angle. Our results establish a physically grounded alternative to traditional TBR models that aligns with experimental observables and enables consistent comparison across boundaries with complex geometries.

Keywords: ThermoReflectance, thermal transport, heat conduction, grain boundaries, Gibbs Excess, beam offset, anisotropy

1 Introduction

Thermal transport in crystalline materials can become direction-dependent due to intrinsic material anisotropy or the presence of structural defects. However, characterizing

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this behavior remains a significant challenge. In particular, grain boundaries have been observed to significantly suppress thermal conductivity in their local vicinity [4, 5], but previous studies attempting to quantify the effects of this suppression on thermal transport [1] often neglect its directional dependence.

In general, interface resistances such as those due to grain boundaries are typically represented numerically by a single value R_B , which is a proportionality constant between the temperature jump due to the interface and the flux normal to the interface as shown in Figure 1. In this model, the interface is treated as an infinitely thin boundary that induces a temperature discontinuity.

Figure 1: Traditional Definition of Interface Resistance

While this simplified model is useful for numerical modeling, it overlooks the fact that physical interfaces such as grain boundaries typically have a finite width due to misalignment between neighboring crystals as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Finite Grain Boundary

In this work, we propose an alternative framework to quantify interface-induced thermal resistance without relying on the idealized thin-interface approximation, which we call the ‘‘Gibbs Excess’’ methodology. The Gibbs Excess approach has been used in previous works [5, 1], and this work seeks to provide a rigorous mathematical background for it. This novel approach accounts for the finite size of a grain boundary and offers a consistent way to extract thermal resistance from different experimental setups, including grain boundaries with different thicknesses and tilt angles. While there are limitations to this proposed framework, we demonstrate how the Gibbs Excess approach provides an alternative to traditional measurement techniques which also have limitations of their own which we shall discuss.

To validate and apply this framework, we leverage Frequency Domain ThermoReflectance (FDTR), a widely used experimental method for probing thermal properties [14, 11, 12, 13]. In FDTR, thermal properties are correlated to the phase lag between a modulated heating source, or pump laser, and the induced temperature oscillations measured by a probe laser. One advantage of FDTR is that it depends solely on the harmonic components of the heating and sensing profiles, thereby reflecting the steady state response of the material [8], making it computationally efficient for numerical simulations.

While standard FDTR configurations use concentrically placed Gaussian-like pump and probe beams to assess cross-plane thermal conductivity, we shall introduce a modification to the pump laser which enables more accurate characterization of material anisotropy, including those induced by defects. Beam modification techniques such as beam offsets have been previously applied to improve sensitivity to in-plane thermal transport [10, 9, 2], and an annular beam profile has been successfully used in Time-Domain ThermoReflectance (TDTR) experiments [7]. In this work, we shall adapt the annular beam profile to FDTR, demonstrating how a ring-shaped pump beam offers improved sensitivity to anisotropic thermal conductivity measurements.

The content of this work is structured as follows: first, a mathematical framework for the modified FDTR setup is introduced, with numerical results demonstrating how it improves on standard FDTR. Next, the Gibbs Excess formulation is derived and validated in 1D, and an extension to a 3D setup as in FDTR is described. Simulation results exhibiting the utility of Gibbs Excess in FDTR experiments are then presented with several numerical examples illustrating different application cases, showing how anisotropic thermal boundary resistance can be characterized through the Gibbs Excess methodology combined with the modified pump laser.

2 FDTR Analytical Framework for the Annular Pump Beam

The complex-valued thermal response of a material in an FDTR setup is given as [2]:

$$\hat{H}(\omega) = \int_0^\infty \bar{\bar{G}}(k, \omega) \bar{\bar{q}}(k, \omega) \bar{\bar{S}}(k, \omega) k dk \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\bar{G}}(k, \omega)$ is the Hankel transform of the surface temperature increase in a multi-layered material subject to a sinusoidally oscillating heat flux $\bar{\bar{q}}(k, \omega)$ (with $\omega = 2\pi f$, f

being the frequency of the oscillation) applied to that same surface through a pump laser [12]. $\hat{S}(k, \omega)$ refers to the probe, or sensing laser which reads the temperature increase on the surface through the reflectivity of the transducer, applying a form of "weighting" to the thermal response. We shall use $\hat{}$ and $\bar{}$ indicators to refer to expressions in the Fourier and Hankel space respectively, with the Hankel transform defined here as:

$$F(k) = \int_0^\infty r J_0(kr) f(r) dr \quad (2)$$

The phase, ϕ , which is used to fit thermal properties, is then calculated as:

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Im[\hat{H}(\omega)]}{\Re[\hat{H}(\omega)]} \right) \quad (3)$$

In standard FDTR setups, the pump laser is usually described as a simple Gaussian profile:

$$\hat{q}(r, \omega) = \frac{2Q_0}{\pi w_0^2} \exp\left(-\frac{2r^2}{w_0^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

That is, a normalized Gaussian expression multiplied by the absorbed pump power, Q_0 . The expression for the probe is similarly given as:

$$\hat{S}(r, \omega) = \frac{2}{\pi w_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{2r^2}{w_1^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

Where w_0 and w_1 are the $1/e^2$ beam waists for the pump and probe respectively.

When the pump beam is offset by a distance x_0 to improve in-plane sensitivity, the radial symmetry of the pump and probe collapses. However, by applying the coordinate transformation $x = r \cos(\theta)$ and $y = r \sin(\theta)$ and integrating this expression over θ [2], the offset pump can be converted to a ring shaped profile of reduced intensity, i.e:

$$\hat{q}(r, \omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{2Q_0}{\pi w_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{2[(r \cos(\theta) - x_0)^2 + (r \sin(\theta))^2]}{w_1^2}\right) d\theta \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{2Q_0}{\pi w_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{2(r^2 + x_0^2)}{w_1^2}\right) I_0\left(\frac{4x_0 r}{w_1^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

With I_0 referring to the zero-order modified Bessel function of the first kind. While this expression was initially derived to improve the numerical efficiency of the fitting process for offset beams, we intend to directly apply a ring shaped profile to the transducer surface. However, in applying this expression to numerical simulations, it was found to be unstable for large offsets (roughly $> 5 \mu m$) due to the exponential growth of the argument of the I_0 term causing issues with numerical precision. Hence, we use the expression for a super-Gaussian ring, which is more general and accommodates non-standard Gaussian profiles (i.e $n \neq 2.0$) which might emerge during experimental implementation of the ring-shaped pump beam:

$$\hat{q}(r, \omega) = \frac{2Q_0 A}{\pi w_1^2} \exp\left(-\frac{2(r - x_0)^n}{w_1^2}\right) \quad (8)$$

where A is a normalization factor for the super-Gaussian expression in order to keep the definition of Q_0 consistent. It should be noted that A can be approximated with low accuracy, since the amplitude of the input signal has no effect on the phase.

Figure 3: Sensitivity Comparison

Figure 3 shows sensitivity curves for silicon material parameters (see Appendix 8.1), comparing a regular Gaussian pump beam and a ring-shaped super-Gaussian pump with an offset of $x_0 = 5 \mu m$. In the super-Gaussian plot, we see clearly how the sensitivity to in-plane thermal conductivity is higher at lower frequencies, with the cross-plane thermal conductivity more sensitive at higher frequencies. This is expected, as the temperature has more time to spread in the in-plane direction between pulses at lower frequencies.

Figure 4: Brute Force Error Surface Comparison

Figure 4 shows the error surface for both cases, clearly showing a steepening in the curve for the super-Gaussian case. This confirms the increased sensitivity and faster solution convergence of the ring-shaped pump profile.

Figure 5: Sensitivity vs Offset for in-plane kappa

We then investigate the effect of offset distance on the sensitivity of the fit. Figure 5 shows how the sensitivity continues to increase with offset before asymptotically reaching a constant value once the super-Gaussian offset radius is sufficiently far from the probe origin.

However, in practice, the offset should be terminated at or less than the penetration depth, which is a length scale at which the temperature can be assumed to decay to 0.99 of its original value and can be considered undetectable by the finite spot size probe laser. The penetration depth, δ is defined as:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\kappa}{\pi f \rho c_p}} \quad (9)$$

where κ is the thermal conductivity, f is the modulation frequency, ρ is the material density, and c_p is the specific heat capacity.

While annular FDTR enhances directional sensitivity, interpreting the data near interfaces requires a more robust framework. We now introduce the Gibbs Excess formalism to address this need.

3 Gibbs Excess Framework

In crystalline semiconductors such as silicon, heat is primarily carried by quantized lattice vibrations known as phonons. These vibrations propagate through the crystal lattice, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Phonon Propagation in Crystalline Materials

The rate at which phonons decay, or “scatter”, is influenced by intrinsic material properties such as atomic mass, bond strength, and crystal structure. This behavior is typically characterized by the material’s thermal conductivity, κ , a parameter that quantifies the ease with which heat is transported through the lattice.

Grain boundaries accelerate this phonon scattering by interfering with the wave propagation due to the disorder of the atoms within the region as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Grain Boundary Scattering

This phonon scattering correlates to a reduction in thermal conductivity, typically modeled through a “suppression function”. While suppression function modeling is still an active

area of research [6], we shall represent grain boundaries as finite regions of constant, reduced thermal conductivity to simplify expressions as we demonstrate the mathematical framework behind the Gibbs Excess Resistance.

3.1 Gibbs Excess in 1D

Consider a 1D heating profile as in Figure 8, centered at the origin. In this model, the motion of individual atoms is abstracted away under the continuum assumption, that is, we assume that the Fourier Heat Equation, given in Equation 10, applies.

$$q = -\kappa \frac{dT}{dx} \tag{10}$$

Figure 8: 1D Heat Transport

Figure 9 then illustrates three different cases - no temperature jump, a finite, diffuse "grain boundary", and a perfect, infinitely thin interface.

Figure 9: No Interface vs Diffuse/Finite Interface vs Perfect Interface

In this formulation, our attention shall be focused on the diffuse grain boundary, as naturally occurring interfaces have a diffuse effect as previously shown in Figure 2 - the perfect interface is a continuum approximation. The excess temperature jump across the boundary ΔT_{excess} is defined as the additional temperature drop due to the reduced thermal conductivity of the boundary, and is given as:

$$\Delta T_{excess} = \int_{-l}^{+l} \left(\left[\frac{dT}{dx} \right]_{bulk} - \left[\frac{dT}{dx} \right]_{loc} \right) dx \quad (11)$$

Where l is some distance sufficiently far from the boundary such that the boundary has negligible effect on its thermal conductivity. Substituting the Fourier heat equation, i.e $q = -\kappa \frac{dT}{dx}$, we get:

$$\Delta T_{excess} = \int_{-l}^{+l} \left(\frac{q}{\kappa_{loc}(x)} - \frac{q}{\kappa_{bulk}} \right) dx \quad (12)$$

In the traditional interface resistance definition described in Figure 1, continuity in the flux across a boundary is enforced through the following expression in 1D:

$$q^+ = q^- = -\frac{1}{R_B} \Delta T \quad (13)$$

We adapt the same expression to define a resistance quantity, R_{gibbs} , which measures the excess resistance due to the GB, i.e:

$$q^+(\epsilon) = q^-(\epsilon) = -\frac{1}{R_{gibbs}} \Delta T_{excess} \quad (14)$$

Where $q(\epsilon)$ is the value of the flux on either side of the grain boundary, which must be equivalent to enforce continuity in the flux just as in the continuum case. That is,

$$\text{grain boundary width} = 2\epsilon \quad (15)$$

Substituting in Equation (12), we obtain the following expression:

$$R_{gibbs} = \frac{1}{q(\epsilon)} \int_{-l}^{+l} \left(\frac{q(x)}{\kappa_{loc}(x)} - \frac{q(x)}{\kappa_{bulk}} \right) dx \quad (16)$$

In 1D, the flux is constant across the material, thereby defining the Gibbs Excess Resistance, R_{gibbs} as:

$$R_{gibbs} = \int_{-l}^{+l} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa_{loc}(x)} - \frac{1}{\kappa_{bulk}} \right) dx \quad (17)$$

3.1.1 Numerical Validation of 1D Gibbs Excess

Consider a 1D heating profile as in Figure 10. Assume S.I. units for all quantities.

Figure 10: 1D Heat Profile with Grain Boundary

We assume the Fourier's Equation holds across the material. That is,

$$q = -\kappa \frac{dT}{dx} \quad (18)$$

In discrete form, this equation can be rewritten as:

$$q = -\kappa \frac{\Delta T}{d} \quad (19)$$

where d is the distance across which the temperature drops by ΔT . Substituting Equation 13, we can then define the resistance, R , as:

$$R = \frac{d}{\kappa} \quad (20)$$

This expression has been commonly used to approximate the resistance (or its inverse, the conductance) across a grain boundary [1]. In this case, it means the total resistance across both ends of the material can be decomposed into a series sum of individual resistances, i.e:

$$R_{total} = \underbrace{\frac{d_{left}}{\kappa_{bulk}}}_{R_{left}} + \underbrace{\frac{d_{GB}}{\kappa_{GB}}}_{R_B} + \underbrace{\frac{d_{right}}{\kappa_{bulk}}}_{R_{right}} \quad (21)$$

This implies that the grain boundary in Figure 10 can be replaced by an infinitely thin boundary with resistance R_B as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Grain Boundary Replaced by Resistance

However, this alters the geometry of the initial system, and makes it difficult to include multiphysics effects such as thermal expansion, chemical reactions, etc. if there is a need to. In the context of nanoscale thermal transport, although grain boundaries typically have a much smaller width in comparison to the bulk system being analyzed, this modification still cannot be ignored. Thus, the Gibbs Excess methodology seeks to preserve the original geometry while presenting a robust means for quantifying the boundary resistance that is also experimentally feasible.

Finite Element (FE) simulations were run on a system with the same parameters as Figure 10, and the temperature profile was plotted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Temperature Profile Across x

This implies a measured temperature drop of 219.02 K across the boundary. Using the Gibbs Excess methodology, we seek to decompose this temperature drop into its individual parts, i.e:

$$\Delta T_{total} = \Delta T_{bulk} + \Delta T_{excess} \quad (22)$$

That is, ΔT_{bulk} is the temperature drop if that region had the same thermal conductivity as the rest of the bulk material, and ΔT_{excess} is the excess temperature drop captured by the Gibbs Excess approach. To carry out this temperature drop decomposition, we first calculate the derivative of the temperature profile, $-\frac{dT}{dx}$, and solve for ΔT_{excess} as given previously in Equation 11. The temperature gradient plot is given in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Temperature Gradient Profile Across x

This resulted in a ΔT_{excess} value of 124.10 K . ΔT_{bulk} was then calculated using the discrete approximation from Equation 19, i.e:

$$\Delta T_{bulk} = \left[\frac{dT}{dx} \right]_{bulk} \times d_{GB} = 4.799 \times 20 = 95.98 \text{ K} \quad (23)$$

This results in a total temperature drop, ΔT_{total} , calculated through Gibbs Excess:

$$\Delta T_{total} = 124.10 + 95.98 = \mathbf{220.08 \text{ K} \approx 219.02 \text{ K}} \quad (24)$$

That is, the total temperature drop calculated through Gibbs Excess is roughly equal to the initial measured temperature drop, thereby validating this methodology. Given the constant flux profile in Figure 14 (with numerical artifacts at the boundary transition points), we can now calculate the boundary resistance, R_{gibbs} , preserving the original geometry of the system and replacing the GB by an infinitely thin resistance.

Figure 14: Heat Flux Profile Across x

$$R_{gibbs} = \frac{\Delta T_{excess}}{q} = 0.199 \text{ (m}^2 \cdot \text{K)}/\text{W} \quad (25)$$

Figure 15: Grain Boundary Replaced by R_{gibbs}

3.2 Gibbs Excess Extension to 3D

The generalization of the Gibbs Excess methodology to 3D is not trivial. We present here a formulation for a grain boundary centered at the origin with no cross-sectional variance in size or orientation as shown in Figure 16. In this case, the phase is sampled at different locations across the sample through the FDTR technique, and an effective thermal conductivity profile, $\kappa_{loc}(x)$ is obtained by fitting each phase to the analytical solution presented in Equation 1. Due to the modification of the pump laser, $\kappa_{loc}(x)$ can be fitted as an anisotropic effective thermal conductivity tensor. That is, the effective thermal conductivity profiles in the cross-plane and in-plane directions can be simultaneously fitted.

Figure 16: Gibbs Excess FDTR methodology - Finite Interface

Starting from the same point as Equation (11), but instead defining the temperature jump across the normal to the interface, this results in Equation (26)

$$\Delta T_{excess} = \int_{-l}^{+l} ([\nabla T \cdot \mathbf{n}]_{bulk} - [\nabla T \cdot \mathbf{n}]_{loc}) dx \quad (26)$$

Again, substituting the Fourier heat equation:

$$\Delta T_{excess} = \int_{-l}^{+l} ([(\kappa_{loc}^{-1} \mathbf{q}) \cdot \mathbf{n}] - [(\kappa_{bulk}^{-1} \mathbf{q}) \cdot \mathbf{n}]) dx \quad (27)$$

The interface jump is now related through the normal component of the flux, i.e

$$\mathbf{q}^+ \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{q}^- \cdot \mathbf{n} = -\frac{1}{R_{gibbs}} \Delta T_{excess} \quad (28)$$

Substituting in Equation 27 and applying tensor operations, we obtain the following expression for the Gibbs Excess Resistance, R_{gibbs} :

$$R_{gibbs} = \frac{\int_{-l}^{+l} ([\kappa_{loc}^{-1} : \mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{n}] - [\kappa_{bulk}^{-1} : \mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{n}]) dx}{\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n}} \quad (29)$$

That is, similar to the 1D case:

$$R_{gibbs} = \frac{\Delta T_{excess}}{\text{boundary flux}} \quad (30)$$

To make further simplifications, Equation 29 can be written suggestively as:

$$R_{gibbs} = \int_{-l}^{+l} \left(\left[\kappa_{loc}^{-1} : \frac{\mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{n}}{\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n}} \right] - \left[\kappa_{bulk}^{-1} : \frac{\mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{n}}{\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n}} \right] \right) dx \quad (31)$$

Due to the difficulty in obtaining the flux profile experimentally, we non-trivially assume that the flux tensor, which we shall call $\mathbb{Q} = \frac{\mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{n}}{\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{n}}$, is constant along the x axis, thus pulling it out of the integral due to the linear and distributive property of the double contraction. This results in the following expression for R_{gibbs} :

$$R_{gibbs} = \left(\int_{-l}^{+l} (\kappa_{loc}^{-1} - \kappa_{bulk}^{-1}) dx \right) : \mathbb{Q} \quad (32)$$

We now define the quantity inside the integral as a tensor, \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} as an anisotropic, qualitative measure of interface resistance which is similar to the 1D resistance. That is,

$$R_{gibbs} = \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} : \mathbb{Q} \quad (33)$$

While this quantity, \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} , is based on key assumptions that remain uncertain, we find this approximation useful for qualitative measurement of grain boundary thermal resistance as shall be demonstrated through numerical results in the following section.

3.2.1 Gibbs Excess in 3D: Perfect Interface

To demonstrate the utility of the approximation laid out in the previous section, we apply the Gibbs Excess Methodology to the limiting case, i.e a perfect interface as illustrated in Figure 17

Figure 17: Gibbs Excess FDTR methodology - Perfect/Sharp Interface

Since the infinitely thin boundary is placed perpendicular to the heating source, we expect near zero vertical resistance in the vertical direction relative to the horizontal direction. To calculate \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} , we first obtain the effective thermal conductivity profile, $\kappa_{loc}(x)$. Owing to the anisotropic sensitivity afforded by the ring-shaped pump laser, $\kappa_{loc}(x)$ can be obtained as a diagonal tensor consisting of radial and cross-plane components of the thermal conductivity, $\kappa_r(x)$ and $\kappa_z(x)$, which are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Effective κ , Perfect Interface

It is interesting to note the shape of the cross-plane thermal conductivity profile, $\kappa_z(x)$, which we expect to be net constant and equal to κ_{bulk} . The obtained results nearly match theoretical expectations, with what appears to be an artificial boost followed by an immediate, roughly equal reduction in the thermal conductivity. Calculating R_{gibbs} for both directions, we observe that the vertical thermal resistance is significantly smaller than the horizontal component, aligning with our predictions. Table 1.

Table 1: Decomposition of Gibbs Excess Resistance from Anisotropic FDTR Simulations. All resistance values are in $\text{TW}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^2$.

Direction	Side	Bulk κ (W/m·K)	Resistance	Boost	Net Resistance
Z (Cross-plane)	Left	130.1865	62.45	54.10	8.36
	Right	130.1864	60.17	54.75	5.41
	Total	–	122.62	108.85	13.77
R (In-plane)	Left	130.2108	263.52	4.98	258.54
	Right	130.2245	270.71	0.98	269.74
	Total	–	534.23	5.95	528.28

The recovered “bulk” thermal conductivity is close to the prescribed value, i.e 130 (W/m·K), with a small allowance for numerical errors. The contrast in the magnitudes of the resistances for both directions is clearly visualized in the bar chart in Figure 19, showing clearly the utility of Gibbs Excess for qualitative analysis of grain boundaries.

Figure 19: Gibbs Excess Resistance for Perfect Interface

3.2.2 Gibbs Excess in 3D: Finite Interface

To provide another numerical example, the Gibbs Excess methodology was applied to a finite interface as described earlier in Figure 16. The anisotropic thermal conductivity profiles are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Effective κ , Finite Interface

Unlike the perfect interface, we see a finite thermal conductivity drop in the cross plane direction, suggesting that the Gibbs Excess can qualitatively differentiate between different boundary thicknesses. This is particularly useful for comparing experimental boundary measurements on different boundaries within the same sample. We also observe what appears to be a “kink” in the thermal conductivity profile at around $5 \mu\text{m}$, which could potentially be explained by the radius of the annular pump having the same value.

Again, the calculated resistances, R_{gibbs} , are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Decomposition of Gibbs Excess Resistance for Finite Interface Simulation. All resistance values are in $\text{TW}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^2$.

Direction	Side	Bulk κ (W/m·K)	Resistance	Boost	Net Resistance
Z (Cross-plane)	Left	130.1865	157.53	0.00	157.53
	Right	130.1864	155.55	0.17	155.37
	Total	–	313.08	0.17	312.90
R (In-plane)	Left	130.2107	223.83	4.99	218.84
	Right	130.2243	230.57	0.60	229.97
	Total	–	454.39	5.58	448.81

This time, we see a clear vertical resistance, which is expected due to the finite width of the boundary. With these results, we conclude that the Gibbs Excess provides a reasonable qualitative measure of grain boundary thermal resistance.

Figure 21: Gibbs Excess Resistance for Finite Interface

3.2.3 Angled Boundaries

The Gibbs Excess methodology is based on the assumption that the scan direction is perpendicular to the boundary. When the boundary is tilted by an angle θ but the scanning direction remains in the cartesian x direction, we need to update the “gibbs direction” as illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Gibbs Excess on Angled Boundaries

The scanning direction is related to this “gibbs direction” as:

$$\text{scanning direction} = \frac{\text{gibbs direction}}{\sin \alpha} = \frac{\text{gibbs direction}}{\cos \theta} \quad (34)$$

Our previous works employing the Gibbs Excess methodology without directional resolution (i.e, fitting \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} as an isotropic tensor) have confirmed this with the calculated resistance observed to scale as $1/\cos \theta$ as the tilt angle increased, aligning with theoretical expectations [6].

Figure 23: Tilt Angle vs R_{gibbs}

With the anisotropic resolution afforded by the annular pump beam, we now present the

in-plane and cross-plane effective thermal conductivity profiles with increasing θ angle in Figures 24 and 25:

Figure 24: Effective Thermal Conductivity κ_{loc} , with increasing θ (R Component)

Figure 25: Effective Thermal Conductivity κ_{loc} , with increasing θ (Z Component)

We observe a much faster increase in thermal conductivity suppression in the z direction, which we attribute to a potential confinement effect between the heat source and the boundary due to the increasingly horizontal orientation of the boundary.

Figure 26: Anisotropic Fit of Tilt Angle, θ , vs R_{gibbs}

Figure 26 then plots the directionally-resolved excess resistance. Similar to the isotropic case, the excess resistance is observed to scale as $1/\cos\theta$ in the in-plane direction. However, we find that the resistance in the cross-plane direction scales roughly as $1/\cos^2\theta$, and we attribute this additional resistance to the confinement effect hypothesized earlier. Overall, the results of this analysis provide evidence that the orientation of the boundary relative to the direction of the heat source significantly influences the thermal resistance it contributes.

4 Limitations of Traditional Grain Boundary Measurement Methods

As mentioned earlier in Section 3.1, the d/κ approximation for interface resistance requires alteration of the material geometry. To circumvent that problem, inverse fitting methods as in Figure 27 could potentially be used:

Figure 27: Traditional Grain Boundary Inverse Fitting

However, to fit grain boundary resistance to Equation 1, each layer must be perfectly horizontal, as that is a main assumption of the analytical solution. To avoid this issue it is possible to use Finite Element Modeling for the inverse fitting, but due to the nature of the “Perfect Interface” being fitted, it is difficult and computationally expensive to do so.

Additionally, the inconsistency of the results across different finite element sizes makes accurate comparison between boundaries difficult, as shown in Table 3, where we implemented the boundary resistance calculated in Section 3.1.1. This inconsistency could be more pronounced when modeling grain boundaries which are typically orders of magnitude smaller in thickness than bulk material in typical sample setups.

Table 3: Temperature Drops for Varying Element Sizes

Element size / L_{total}	T_{left} (K)	T_{right} (K)	ΔT (K)
0.00416	690.00	609.90	80.10
0.00833	714.17	585.89	128.28
0.02083	706.34	593.80	112.54
Analytical	712.06	587.96	124.10

A similar inconsistency was observed while attempting to fit a grain boundary in a setup similar to Figure 27, with the computed value varying further with the depth of grain boundary placement. On the other hand, the resistance calculated through Gibbs Excess is independent of laser spot size, even though the effective thermal conductivity profile may vary. That is, the finer the FDTR spot size resolution, the closer the effective thermal conductivity profile, $\kappa_{loc}(x)$ is to exact conditions, with larger spot sizes “smearing” out the effective thermal conductivity. Therefore, the Gibbs Excess methodology provides an improvement on traditional methods in the consistency of measurements across boundaries on the same sample, while also enabling easy measurement of boundaries with complex geometries.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we developed a rigorous framework to characterize directional grain boundary (GB) thermal resistance by integrating a modified Frequency Domain ThermoReflectance (FDTR) experimental setup with the Gibbs Excess methodology. Our introduction of a super-Gaussian ring-shaped pump beam significantly enhanced the directional sensitivity of FDTR, enabling simultaneous resolution of in-plane and cross-plane thermal conductivity components. Numerical sensitivity analyses and brute-force fitting confirmed that the annular beam profile improves both convergence and parameter decoupling.

To quantify thermal boundary resistance while preserving the geometry of the interface, we extended the Gibbs Excess formalism to both 1D and 3D. In 1D, we validated the method with finite element simulations and showed that it reliably decomposes the total temperature drop into bulk and excess contributions. In 3D, we proposed a tensorial formulation for the excess resistance and introduced an anisotropic resistance tensor \mathbb{R}_{gibbs} as a qualitative descriptor of interfacial resistance. This approach proved effective for distinguishing between perfect and finite interfaces, as well as capturing directional variations in resistance due to boundary tilt angle.

We also highlighted the shortcomings of traditional GB resistance modeling methods, including the loss of geometric fidelity and sensitivity to mesh size in finite element inverse fitting. In contrast, the Gibbs Excess framework does not require alteration of the sample

geometry and can be used to measure excess boundary resistances across a variety of widths and tilt angles.

Future work may explore several key directions including: (1) implementing nano-scale FDTR with smaller spot sizes to experimentally verify whether the boosts in cross-plane effective thermal conductivity near the boundary observed in the perfect interface case is a numerical artifact or a physical reality; (2) experimentally or numerically confirming the assumption of constant flux in FDTR, which underlies our decision to bring \mathbb{Q} out of the integral in the 3D Gibbs Excess derivation; and (3) potentially applying the Gibbs Excess methodology experimentally to measure resistances produced by non-planar, curved, or spatially varying boundaries.

Altogether, this study presents a geometry-respecting, directionally resolved, and experimentally integrable framework for characterizing grain boundary thermal resistance. In summary, the Gibbs Excess methodology provides an alternative measure of interface resistance that takes the direction of the heating source into account, something the traditional measure R_B does not do. When combined with enhanced FDTR sensitivity, this technique opens a promising path toward deeper understanding and consistent quantification of interfacial thermal transport phenomena.

6 Authorship Statement

All simulations, analysis, and writing were conducted by the first author. Co-authors provided feedback during lab meetings. This preprint is posted to document the methodology and findings while formal journal submission is under consideration.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Simulation Properties

Table 4: Simulation and Material Parameters

Parameter	Symbol / Value	Units
Geometry		
Grain boundary width	1×10^{-6}	m
Transducer thickness (Au)	9×10^{-8}	m
Pump radius	1.53×10^{-6}	m
Probe radius	1.34×10^{-6}	m
Pump Offset Distance/Ring Radius	5×10^{-6}	m
Experimental Parameters		
Absorbed pump power (Q_0A)	0.01	W
Au-Si boundary conductance	3×10^7	W/(m ² ·K)
Si-Si conductance (for perfect interface)	5.6×10^8	W/(m ² ·K)
Frequencies sampled	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10	MHz
Material Properties		
<u>Silicon (Si) - Sample</u>		
Bulk thermal conductivity	130	W/(m·K)
Grain boundary thermal conductivity	56.52	W/(m·K)
Density (ρ_{Si})	2329	kg/m ³
Heat capacity (c_p^{Si})	689.1	J/(kg·K)
<u>Gold (Au) - Transducer</u>		
Bulk thermal conductivity	215	W/(m·K)
Density (ρ_{Au})	19300	kg/m ³
Heat capacity (c_p^{Au})	128.7	J/(kg·K)

8.2 FDTR Finite Element Implementation Details

This section lays out the full implementation details of the Finite Element Model used to simulate FDTR experiments in this work. These simulations were carried out using the open-source MOOSE Framework [3] and run on a High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster. To improve the computational efficiency of the simulations, they were implemented in the frequency domain, since the experimental method similarly depends solely on the harmonic components of the heating and sensing laser profiles. Before carrying out any simulations, the model was rigorously validated with the integral-transform based analytical solution [12], and the computed phase values matched with high accuracy (up to 4 decimal places).

The simulation domain consists of a $320 \times 160 \times 40.09 \mu\text{m}$ box, with the extended x and y directions intended to simulate infinite domains in those directions, and the z profile modeling a semi-infinite domain.

Figure 28: FDTR Finite Element Mesh

In the z direction the transducer is assumed to be 90 nm thick, with material properties for Gold (Au) applied from $0 < z < 0.09 \mu\text{m}$. Silicon (Si) material properties are used for substrate, i.e the rest of the domain from $-40 < z < 0 \mu\text{m}$.

The minimum element size is $4 \mu\text{m}$, which is used for the bulk of the domain. However, closer to the applied heat source, the elements within the transducer have a side length of $0.045 \mu\text{m}$, and within the substrate the elements are $0.075 \mu\text{m}$ large for $0 < r < 4 \mu\text{m}$, and $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ large for $4 < r < 8 \mu\text{m}$, where $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$. The element sizes smoothly transition in between, ensuring proper resolution of the temperature profile, as the penetration depth is roughly $5 \mu\text{m}$ based on the material properties provided in Section 8.1. For each scan location along the x direction, the mesh refinement was updated accordingly. The equations governing the simulations are now presented in the following subsection.

8.2.1 Frequency Domain Equation Setup

Fourier Heat Equation

Since these simulations were run at frequencies within the diffusive regime for heat transport in silicon (i.e ≤ 10 MHz), the Fourier Heat Equation is assumed to apply, i.e:

$$\kappa \nabla^2 T - \rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (35)$$

where κ is the thermal conductivity, ρ is the density, c_p is the heat capacity, and T is the temperature profile. Taking the temporal Fourier Transform, i.e from $T(\mathbf{x}, t)$ to $\hat{T}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$, this equation becomes:

$$\kappa \nabla^2 \hat{T} - i\omega \rho c_p \hat{T} = 0 \quad (36)$$

where i is the imaginary number such that $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

Boundary Condition - Applied Flux

In the time domain, the applied flux can be modeled as:

$$q(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) = \text{Pump}(\mathbf{r}) \times (1 - \cos(2\pi f t)) \quad (37)$$

Where $\text{Pump}(\mathbf{r})$ is the expression for the shape of the heating profile (regular Gaussian, super-Gaussian ring, etc.) multiplied by a sinusoidal function defined in such a way that the temperature never falls below zero, making it physically realistic. The term f is the heating frequency. In the frequency domain, however, we are only concerned with the harmonic portion of this profile. Therefore, the applied flux becomes:

$$q(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = -\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla \hat{T}) = \text{Pump}(\mathbf{r}) \times \delta(\omega - 2\pi f) \quad (38)$$

All other boundaries are assumed to be zero-flux boundaries.

Interface Condition

The interface condition in the real space uses the continuum approximation defined in Equation 13. That is,

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla T^+) = -\frac{1}{R}(T^- - T^+) \quad (39)$$

and

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla T^-) = -\frac{1}{R}(T^+ - T^-) \quad (40)$$

where the $+$ and $-$ superscripts denote either side of the interface, thereby enforcing continuity in the flux. In the Fourier space, these expression are simply replaced by their frequency domain counterparts, i.e:

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla \hat{T}^+) = -\frac{1}{R}(\hat{T}^- - \hat{T}^+) \quad (41)$$

and

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot (\kappa \nabla \hat{T}^-) = -\frac{1}{R}(\hat{T}^+ - \hat{T}^-) \quad (42)$$

Initial Conditions

The initial conditions in the real space assume the material starts at room temperature. However, in the Fourier space, these conditions are not relevant.

Post-Processor - Probe Laser

The sensing, or probe laser reads the temperature increase integrated over the heating surface, and the phase is computed through the difference between the temperature profile and the heating profile. In the frequency domain, by replacing T with \hat{T} , it reads the complex temperature response detailed in Equation 1. The phase is then computed from the imaginary and real parts as described in Equation 3.

8.2.2 Finite Element Discretization

The Finite Element Implementation of the governing equations goes as follows:

- Decompose $\hat{T}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$ into imaginary and real parts, i.e $\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}, \omega) + i\hat{V}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$.
- Rewrite heat equation as a system of two equations. The interface condition largely remains unchanged, with the temperature simply replaced by the real and imaginary parts.
- The boundary condition (applied heat pump) is fully real, hence it is only applied to $\hat{U}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$.

This section will focus on the Finite Element discretization of the heat equation, since the coupling between the imaginary and real parts of the temperature primarily occurs here. Starting from the frequency-domain heat equation:

$$\kappa \nabla^2 \hat{T} - i\omega \rho c_p \hat{T} = 0 \quad (43)$$

Substituting $\hat{T} = \hat{U} + i\hat{V}$, we can separate the equation into its real and imaginary parts:

$$\kappa \nabla^2 \hat{U} + \omega \rho c_p \hat{V} = 0 \quad (\text{REAL}) \quad (44)$$

$$\kappa \nabla^2 \hat{V} - \omega \rho c_p \hat{U} = 0 \quad (\text{IMAGINARY}) \quad (45)$$

Weak Form: Real Part

Starting with the real part of the heat equation, we attempt to get the “weak form” for the finite element implementation. To do so, we multiply by a test function δu and integrate over the domain where equation applies, which we shall call Ω . In tensor notation, this becomes:

$$\int_{\Omega} [\kappa \hat{U}_{,ii} \delta u + \omega \rho c_p \hat{V} \delta u] d\Omega = 0 \quad (46)$$

From the product rule, we know $(\kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u)_{,i} = \kappa \hat{U}_{,ii} \delta u + \kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u_{,i}$. Substituting in Equation 46:

$$\int_{\Omega} [(\kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u)_{,i} - \kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u_{,i} + \omega \rho c_p \hat{V} \delta u] d\Omega = 0 \quad (47)$$

We then apply the divergence theorem on the $(\kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u)_{,i}$ to apply the boundary conditions on the 2D surfaces, with the rest of the equation considered the “kernel” i.e the part that applies to the 3D part of the domain. This is the weak form of the governing equation.

$$\underbrace{\int_{\partial\Omega} \kappa \hat{U}_{,i} n_i \delta u d\Omega}_{\text{BC}} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} [\kappa \hat{U}_{,i} \delta u_{,i} - \omega \rho c_p \hat{V} \delta u] d\Omega}_{\text{Kernel}} = 0 \quad (48)$$

Weak Form: Imaginary Part

We obtain the weak form of the imaginary part through a similar process.

$$- \underbrace{\int_{\partial\Omega} \kappa \hat{V}_{,i} n_i \delta v d\Omega}_{\text{BC}} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} [\kappa \hat{V}_{,i} \delta v_{,i} + \omega \rho c_p \hat{U} \delta v] d\Omega}_{\text{Kernel}} = 0 \quad (49)$$

8.3 Simulation codes

All code and data used for generating thermal measurements in this work are available publicly at <https://github.com/richmondodufisan/purple>.

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